

AN ASSESSMENT OF ONLINE FRAUD ON CUSTOMER RESERVATIONS IN THE HOSPITALITY AND TOURISM INDUSTRY.

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Abstract

This research work examined impact of online fraud committed in the cause of reservation in the hospitality and tourism industry in Ekiti State. It specifically determined various modes of online fraud that are committed in the hospitality and tourism industry; the impact of online fraud in the industry; modes of preventing online fraud in the industry. In view of these three research hypotheses were developed and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Related literatures were examined for the work. The areas of reviewed are: hospitality and tourism industry; private and commercial organisation; characteristics of the industry; most common fraudulent activities in the industry; hospitality and tourism industry management; eco-friendly practices in hospitality and tourism management; skills required to satisfactory hospitality and tourism management. The study embraced descriptive survey method which comprised of staff and customer of hospitality industry in Ekiti State. Simple random sampling technique was used in select ten (10) hospitality and tourism industry and a total of fifty (50) respondents were sampled from the industry. A self-developed questionnaire was used for data collection. Experts in the field of hospitality and tourism industry validated the face and content of the instrument and a reliability coefficient of 0.90 was obtained through split half method. Data Collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics (mean) was used for the test of hypotheses at 0.05 level significance. The result indicated that there were impacts of online fraud committed in the cause of reservation in the hospitality and tourism industry in Ekiti State.

Keyword: Assessment, Online Fraud, Customer, Reservations Hospitality, Tourism, Industry.

Introduction

The term "hospitality" refers to a welcome attitude and way of behaving toward visitors and strangers (Philips, 2018). Being welcoming, entertaining, and hospitable to strangers, guests, and visitors is a big part of this. The Latin word *hospes*, meaning guest, visitor, or someone who provides accommodation for a guest or tourist, is the origin of the English words hospitality and tourism. The foundational premise of hospitality and tourism is that the visitor is paramount. Because of their great importance and the positive impact, they have on one's house, guests and visitors are highly valued and revered (Introduction to Hospitality and tourist management, 2016). Treating guests with kindness is the most important aspect of hospitality and tourist management. Lodging and guest accommodation is the focus of this sector. The hospitality industry encompasses a wide range of subsectors, for example: rooms and catering, event planning, theme parks, travel and tourism, agencies, restaurants, and nightlife. The crime of fraud encompasses all forms of deceit, including but not limited to verbal or nonverbal misrepresentation of truth, making false or misleading claims, or withholding information that should have been made public, with the goal of causing another person harm. The phrase "hospitality" and "tourism" refer to the interaction between hosts and guests, providing care, kindness, and civility to those who are need of it. Unfortunately, fraud is a problem for all types of organisations, including those in our sector. A research conducted by the Association of Certified Fraud Examiners and reported in their 2014 Report to the Nations on Occupational Fraud and Abuse states that fraud causes a 5% annual revenue loss for the average firm. Statistical analysis of the hotel and tourist sector reveals that yearly revenue losses due to staff and customer fraud range from 5% to 6%. A business owner in the hotel and tourist sector, for instance, can lose half a million to 600,000 dollars per year, even though their room income is around \$10 million. Nowadays, it's crucial to exploit people through the use of online services or software that has Internet connectivity in order to commit fraud or take advantage of them. The deployment of malicious security software is a prevalent type of internet fraud. Con artists can utilise online services to trick unsuspecting victims into parting with their money, execute fraudulent transactions, or even send the stolen funds to other parties involved in the scam (Collins, 2021). Neither is the realm of internet transactions related to hospitality and tourism. The majority of hotels, motels, and other businesses in the hospitality and tourist sector now accept payments and accept reservations online. It is possible for reservation transactions to be the target of online fraud. Chat rooms, email, message boards, and websites are all potential entry points for online fraud. Crime, safety, and fire vulnerabilities force the sector to deploy security measures (Abayomi 2025). The hotel and tourist business is a prime target for shoplifters because of the high value of perishable goods kept there, including linens, artwork, decorations, food, visitors' apparel, and cash. No one takes the security of those working in the hotel and tourist industries more seriously than they do. Everyone from guests entering and exiting the

establishment to employees (including those in the kitchen, cleaning, bar and patron repair departments) and security guards are part of the constant stream of people in the hospitality and tourist sector (Zarei, Nuri, & Noroozi, 2019). While everyone working in the hospitality and tourist sector deserves safety, the most vulnerable members of the business are the female employees, female visitors, and children who are on the premises during the night time security shift change and hand-over. When it comes to safeguarding important assets, both internal and external, the hotel and tourist industries rely heavily on effective security measures.

Staff members in the hotel and tourism industries may impersonate this client during the transaction, request payment to an offshore account using an unsubstantiated reason, and then use the stolen credit card to complete the transaction. Hence, this study intends to analyse impact of online fraud committed in the cause of reservation in the Hospitality and tourism industry in Ekiti State.

Statement of Problem

The hospitality and tourism industries place a premium on online booking and reservations. Consequently, there has been a rise in online fraud while making reservations or bookings. There is a wide variety of criminal behaviour that can include the use of computers or the internet to commit fraud. One such method is "hacking," in which an intruder gains remote access to a protected computer or internet site using a variety of technical tools.

The second typical unlawful conduct is to decipher an unauthorised electronic transfer. Data breaches like this can lead to identity theft and other forms of financial fraud by exposing sensitive information like passwords and credit card numbers. Fear, mistrust, financial losses, and even insolvency have all been brought on by the effect of internet fraud on the hotel and tourism sectors. Hence, this study intends to assess the impact of online fraud committed in the cause of reservation in the Hospitality and tourism industry in Ekiti State.

Aim and Objectives of the study.

The following objectives were set;

- i. investigate various ways online fraud are committed in the industry
- ii. evaluate the impact of online fraud in the industry.
- iii. assessing various ways of preventing online fraud in the industry.

Research Questions

1. What are the various modes online fraud is committed in the hospitality and tourism industry?
2. What effect does online fraud has on hospitality and tourism industry.
3. What are the mode of preventing online fraud in the hospitality and tourism industry?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are generated for the study;

1. There is no significant modes online fraud is being committed in the hospitality and tourism industry.
2. There is no significant effect of online fraud on the hospitality and tourism industry.
3. There is no significant modes of preventing online fraud in the hospitality and tourism industry.

Significance of the Study

The research work is high relevance in hospitality and tourism industry, managers and customer, researchers, general public and government. This study was undoubtedly being of immense help to hospitality and tourism owners to know to prevent crime and strategies to put in place. Those in charge of the hospitality and tourist industries will gain from this study because the results will show them how secure the industry is now and whether or not guests are really at a disadvantage if, for example, they pay to stay at a hotel but have their possessions stolen and cannot get their money back. Users in the hospitality and tourist industries will find the research findings illuminating because they will help them evaluate the efficacy of security measures in the industry, determine the most common types of crimes committed in the sector, and measure the level of safety and security perceived by both guests and employees. People are wary of doing business with others online due to the prevalence of online fraud. To that end, the research will shed light on strategies for combating and preventing online fraud, which is a major issue in the travel and hospitality sector. As supplementary reading for future scholars interested in the same topics, this book will also be useful to students studying tourism and hospitality management. Findings of this study will provide an insight into areas reservation in the Hospitality and tourism industry as regards bookings, security and basis for future researchers.

Scope of the Study

This study focused on the impact of online fraud committed in the cause of reservation in the hospitality and tourism industry in Ekiti state.

Review of Related Literature.

If one is interested in a job in the hospitality and tourism sector, they can learn about all the many subsectors that make up the business as a whole. The hospitality and tourism industry encompasses a wide range of disciplines, including but not limited to: human resource management, organisational behaviour, facilities management, employment law, financial and managerial accounting, financial management and operations, career development, organisational administration, human resources, lodging industry introduction, hygiene and food service operations, cost control, organisational administration, and strategic management (Hospitality and tourism Management, 2016). People now expect more from their vacations than in the past; because to technological improvements, more disposable cash, and more affluent lives, people now have higher expectations for the services and amenities they get. The Nigerian hospitality and tourism industry is evolving with the

belief that modernisation, novelty, and innovation are the key drivers of its growth and survival. Some examples of the unique products of this industry include home stays, heritage hotels, boutique hotels, houseboats, tree houses, and luxury trains.

Hospitality and Tourism Industry Management

Hospitality industry provide pleasant interaction, food, lodging, leisure, entertainment, and comfort are some of the many aspects that must be considered in the administration of hospitality and tourism. Hospitality and tourism are important in many contexts, including private residences, social gatherings, and businesses. Traditionally, these sectors have catered to the needs of those in need by providing them with food, lodging, entertainment, and transportation.

Restaurants, cafeterias, and catering have dominated the food service industry; resorts and motels have dominated the lodging industry; amusement parks, attractions, and casinos have dominated the entertainment industry; and airlines, cruise ships, trains, car rentals, and coaches have dominated the travel service industry. In order to maximise profits, businesses in the hospitality and tourism sector strive to provide customers with first-rate services, which in turn encourages a high volume of bookings at their establishments (Introduction to Hospitality and tourism management, 2017). In the field of hospitality and tourist management, food and beverage management has emerged as a crucial profession (Hospitality and tourism management, 2016). The hospitality and tourism industry has also embraced several eco-friendly practices, such as using low-energy lamps for lighting, televisions, radios, air conditioners, fans, heaters, bathroom facilities, water supply, laundry facilities, newspapers, soaps, towels, tables, chairs, bed sheets, pillows, clean drinking water, carpets and so on. Eco-friendly pencils are not actually constructed of wood, but rather of non-toxic polymer with the addition of natural additives. Instead of using recycled cardboard or reprocessed plastic, eco-friendly pens and pencils employ discarded wood. Using a shaft composed of biodegradable materials like talc, clay, or gypsum, wood saver pencils are manufactured. Potted flower-bearing plants are the ones employed in the hospitality and tourism industries since they filter out a wide variety of air contaminants (Introduction to hospitality and tourism management, 2016).

Fraudulent activities in hospitality and tourism industry

Credit Card Fraud.

A significant portion of credit card fraud incidents have their origins in the hotel and tourism business. An outsider (a customer, vendor, or third party) or an insider (an employee) can commit credit card fraud in a variety of ways. Insider credit card theft and fraud can take many forms, some of which are:

False Account Credits. This kind of fraud often happens when customers use their credit cards to pay the entire amount at the checkout counter in the hotel or tourist business. Despite the fact that the hospitality and tourist sector did not get any complaint from the guest, front desk cashier nonetheless

credits the cashier's personal credit card with a "customer complaint" adjustment after the passenger leaves. To combat this form of fraud, the hotel and tourist sector should check the credits without debits report produced by their property management system (PMS) and institute a policy that requires manager consent for any changes to guests' charges. If there are instances of credit card transactions without matching debit charges, this report can find them.

Use of a Skimming Device. The hospitality and tourism industries are not immune to this form of fraud, which is prevalent in quick-service restaurants. Criminal organisations often use low-wage workers to carry out their fraud schemes. Here, the con artist equips a waiter or cashier with a covert portable gadget that reads the magnetic strip of a customer's credit card and steals their information. For every credit card that the employee successfully retrieves, the fraudster pays them. After obtaining the credit card details, criminal organisations utilise them to produce fake cards and charge illegal purchases. Knowing the fraud plan and informing supervisors about it might help reduce the prevalence of this activity. Due of their convenience and mobility, handheld credit card swipe machines have become ubiquitous in European enterprises. Business owners in the US should be aware of the risks associated with this device's possible abuse and put safeguards in place to prevent losses if it becomes popular.

Credit card frauds

Fraudulent Credit Cards.

The criminal commits this sort of fraud when they book a hotel and pay for costs while they are a guest at a hospitality and tourism establishment using a counterfeit credit card. In most cases, the tourism and hospitality sector learns about the fraud after the customer has already paid and the credit card company has reversed the charge. By then, it can be too late to prevent further financial losses. A measure that the hospitality and tourism sectors may take to combat this sort of fraud is to institute a policy wherein, before verifying a customer's reservation, front desk employees are required to compare the customer's name on the credit card with another form of identity, for example driver's license. In addition, customers should be required to check in with the same credit card used to make the reservation in the hospitality and tourism industries that accept advance payments. Also, the front desk has to pay serious attention to same-day check-in bookings since thieves sometimes use stolen credit cards immediately after stealing them to avoid the owner cancelling them.

Hacking.

Hackers usually target the hospitality and tourism business due to the high volume of customers' sensitive credit card information stored in reservation systems. It may take months for an organization to discover about a hack that occurred in their computer system, meaning that they may not realise

the hack occurred at all. The victims of hacking attacks are not the only ones who feel the effects. The operator in the hospitality and tourism sector needs to take action, inform any impacted visitors, get new and enhanced monitoring systems, and employ specialists to determine the extent of the infiltration. A huge financial hit might be made to the hospitality and tourism sectors, which could also hurt their reputations. Helping to avoid such a tragedy is the hospitality and tourism industry's

Vendor Fraud

An example of occupational fraud is vendor fraud, in which the perpetrator illegally uses the accounts payable and/or payment system of an organization to their own benefit. In the hospitality and tourism industries, bogus vendor schemes are a typical kind of vendor fraud. creating a false vendor file that they control and arranging for the organization to pay the false vendor, an accounts payable clerk in the hospitality and tourism industries or a restaurant might commit vendor fraud. Here we have another case of vendor fraud: a chef may place an order with a favourite vendor in exchange for kickbacks, or the vendor may deliver fewer items than requested, and the chef may receive a bribe equal to the difference.

Reduce your vulnerability to this kind of scam by doing the following:

- The creation of a list of authorised vendors;
- New vendor set-up requiring correct authorisations;
- Demanding specific data from prospective vendors to validate their claims;
- Keeping accounts payable responsibilities separate;
- Looking over major vendors' purchasing, and
- Sticking to the policy of checking the vendor invoice for accuracy in terms of both weight and the amount of products received.

Inventory Theft

Theft of this kind, which can happen at the front or rear of a property, is prevalent in the field of hospitality and tourism. The following are a few typical instances:

- Theft of pricey fish and other high-value inventory goods by a chef;
- A barman who had syphoned costly wine into a depleted water bottle before departing for the day;
- A waiter or waitress at a nearby restaurant giving out complimentary meals or beverages to the staff in return for free goods from the stores; or
- A barman who often gives regulars more drinks than they ordered in exchange for larger tips.

Companies can implement controls to reduce the likelihood of various fraudulent practices, such as:

- Establishing a policy for requests;
- Having employees not bring their own bags or backpacks into the office;
- Keeping a closer eye on the kitchen and bar operations;
- The use of covert observers to keep tabs on bartenders; and
- Analysing food and beverage margins and expenses regularly and looking into big deviations

Coupon Fraud

This kind of deception typically happens when a client uses cash to pay for an item. Take the case of a restaurant that advertises a supper deal with a discount voucher. A client dines at the restaurant, pays with cash, and is unaware of or does not possess the coupon. The waiter deducted \$10 from the client's bill and presented a coupon that the waiter got from an advertisement after the customer left the restaurant. After that, the server will send the remaining payment and coupon as if it had come from the client. By checking if a specific server has a disproportionate number of coupons applied to cash-only guest checks, asking management for clearance before redeeming coupons, and sending promotional coupons directly to consumers, restaurants can reduce the likelihood of coupon fraud.

Complimentary and Void Fraud.

- A front-desk staffer in the hospitality and tourism sector takes payment for a two-night stay from a customer, cancels one night due to a "customer complaint," and keeps the one night's hotel charge.
- A waitress takes money from a customer, writes off the whole bill due to "customer displeasure," and keeps the money for themselves.
- A barman takes payment for a drink, gives a "loyal client" a free drink, and keeps the rest of the money for himself.

Keeping track of comped and voided purchases, documenting the rationale for the comp or void, obtaining management clearance for all comped or cancelled transactions, and attaching a comp or void slip to a guest check or invoice are all measures that can assist in avoiding these sorts of fraud. A larger rate of comped or cancelled transactions by a specific front-desk worker, server, or barman warrants an inquiry. In order to detect unusual behaviour, such as an unusually high percentage of rejected or comped checks or coupons applied to cash checks, etc., point-of-sale software may match staff data with restaurant data and alert the appropriate parties. Management may use this data to spot suspicious circumstances and respond appropriately and promptly. One way to reduce the likelihood of internal fraud is to conduct comprehensive background checks before employing anyone, especially for positions involving money or inventory. Another strategy is to establish a policy outlining the steps to take in the event of fraud, and to punish employees severely if they break this policy.

Research Methodology

Research Design

This research work employ a descriptive research analysis to assessment effect of online fraud committed in the cause of reservation in the hospitality and tourism industry in Ekiti State.

Population of the Study

The study was carried out in Ekiti State. The population of the study consists of customer and staff of hospitality and tourism industry in Ekiti State.

Sample and Sampling Technique

The sample size of fifty (50) respondents were used for the study. Ten (10) hospitality and tourism industry was purposively selected for the study.

Method of Data Collection

The administration of the questionnaire will be done by the researcher. The researcher will distribute the questionnaire to the respondents and the completed questionnaires will be collected immediately.

Data presentation and Analysis

The data collected was be analysed using descriptive such as frequency and mean. Presentation and analysis of the data collection from fifty (50) respondents and the discussion of the result was based on the research hypotheses generated.

Research Hypothesis 1

There is no significant ways online fraud is being committed in the hospitality and tourism industry.

Table 1: Mean Ratings on the ways online fraud is being committed in the hospitality and tourism industry.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	\bar{X}	REMARK
1	False Account Credits	4(20) 80	3(15) 45	2(5) 10	1(10) 10	2.90	Agreed
2	Use of a Skimming Device	4(22) 88	3(10) 30	2(16) 32	1(2) 2	3.04	Agreed
3	Fraudulent Credit Cards	4(15) 60	3(25) 75	2(7) 14	1(3) 3	3.04	Agreed
4	Vendor Fraud	4(14) 56	3 (27) 81	2 (8) 16	1(1) 1	3.08	Agreed
5	Inventory Theft	4 (18) 72	3 (14) 42	2(10) 20	1(8) 8	2.84	Agreed

6.	Hacking.	4(8) 32	3 (24) 72	2 (10) 20	1(8) 8	2.64	Agreed
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The average ratings for items 1-6 are 2.90, 3.04, 3.08, 2.84, and 2.64 according to the data shown in Table 2. All of the average ratings are higher than the minimum requirement of 2.50. This means that the respondents agreed that following ways online fraud is being committed in the hospitality and tourism industry: false account credits, use of skimming, device fraudulent, credit cards, vendor fraud, inventory and theft hacking. Cluster means of 2.92 were determined to be greater than the threshold of 2.50. This implies that there was significant ways online fraud is being committed in the hospitality and tourism industry.

Research Hypothesis 2

There is no significant impact of online fraud on the Hospitality and tourism industry.

Table 2: Mean Ratings on impact of online fraud on the Hospitality and tourism industry.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	X	REMARK
7.	Online fraud discourages people from patronizing hospitality and tourism industry.	4(11) 44	3(29) 87	2(5) 10	1(5) 5	2.92	Agreed
8.	Online fraud affect customer loyalty in Hospitality and tourism industry services	4(16) 64	3(18) 54	2(8) 16	1(8) 8	2.84	Agreed
9.	Online fraud betrays the trust people have in Hospitality and tourism industry.	4(23) 92	3(7) 21	2(15) 30	1(5) 5	2.96	Agreed
10.	Security challenges of hospitality and tourism industry are worsen by online fraud.	4(28) 112	3(12) 36	2(6) 12	1(4) 4	3.28	Agreed
11.	Online fraud cause the losses in profitability of hospitality and tourism industry	4(10) 40	3(32) 96	2(5) 10	1(3) 3	2.98	Agreed

Table 2, showed that the mean ratings of items 7-11 are 2.92, 2.84, 2.96, 3.28, and 2.98. All of the average ratings are higher than the minimum requirement of 2.50. This means that the respondents agreed that; online fraud discourages people from patronizing hospitality and tourism industry, online fraud affect customer loyalty in hospitality and tourism industry services Online fraud betrays the trust people have in Hospitality and tourism industry, security challenges of hospitality and tourism industry are worsening by online fraud, and online fraud cause the losses in profitability of hospitality and tourism industry. The cluster means of 3.00 was also revealed to be above the cut-off point of 2.50. Therefore, there was significant impact of online fraud on the Hospitality and tourism industry.

Research Hypothesis 3

There are no significant ways of preventing online fraud in the Hospitality and tourism industry.

Table 3: Mean Ratings on the ways of preventing online fraud in the hospitality and tourism industry.

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	SD	D	X	REMARK
12.	Management of hospitality and tourism industry needs tight security control for their online activities.	4(14) 56	3(28) 84	2(1) 2	1(7) 7	2.98	Agreed
13.	Fraud prevention with sophisticated anti-fraud tools is necessary in hospitality and tourism industry.	4(15) 60	3(26) 98	2(4) 8	1(5) 5	3.42	Agreed
14	Improved fraud detection can help to reduce fraud in hospitality and tourism industry.	4(12) 48	3(18) 44	2(10) 20	1(10) 10	2.54	Disagreed
15	The use of anti-fraud tools in hospitality and tourism industry preserves customer loyalty by reassuring guest that their data and points are secure.	4(26) 104	3(14) 42	2(8) 16	1(2) 2	3.28	Agreed

16	Hospitality industry visual analytics is good for identifying suspicious point transfer activity in hospitality and tourism industry.	4(17) 68	3(28) 84	2(3) 6	1(2) 2	3.20	Agreed
17	Staff of hospitality and tourism industry could make use of vendor tools, including features such as web behavior detection, alert/case management, and link analysis	4 (28) 112	3 (10) 30	2(8) 16	1(4) 4	3.24	Agreed

Table 3 revealed that the mean ratings of items 12-17 are 2.98, 3.42, 2.54, 3.28, 3.20 and 3.24. All of the mean ratings are higher than the minimum requirement of 2.50. This means that the respondents agreed that; management of hospitality and tourism industry needs tight security control for their online activities, fraud prevention with sophisticated anti-fraud tools is necessary in hospitality and tourism industry, increased fraud detection can help to reduce fraud losses in hospitality and tourism industry, the use of anti-fraud tools in hospitality and tourism industry preserves customer loyalty by reassuring members that their data and points are secure, hospitality industry visual analytics is good for identifying suspicious point transfer activity in hospitality and tourism industry, and staff of hospitality and tourism industry could make use of vendor tools, including capabilities like link analysis, alert/case management, and web behaviour detection. In addition, the cluster mean of 3.11 was determined to be more than the threshold of 2.50. This suggests that the Hospitality and Tourism sectors had substantial measures in place to combat internet fraud.

Discussion of the Findings

The finding of the study in hypotheses one sought to determine ways online fraud is being committed in the hospitality and tourism industry and it was revealed that false account credits; use of theft hacking, skimming, vendor fraud inventory, device fraudulent, and credit cards. Hence, there was significant ways online fraud is being committed in the hospitality and tourism industry. The null hypothesis one was rejected which confirmed that there was significant ways online fraud is being committed in the hospitality and tourism industry.

The finding of the study in hypothesis two sought to determine impact of online fraud on the Hospitality and tourism industry and it was revealed that online fraud discourages people from patronizing hospitality and tourism industry, online fraud affect customer loyalty in hospitality and tourism industry services Online fraud betrays the trust people have in Hospitality and tourism industry, security challenges of hospitality and tourism industry are worsening by online fraud, and online fraud cause the losses in profitability of hospitality and tourism industry. Hence, there was significant impact of online fraud on the Hospitality and tourism industry. The null hypothesis two was rejected which confirmed that there was significant impact of online fraud on the industry.

The finding of the study in hypotheses three sought to determine ways of preventing online fraud in the Hospitality and tourism industry and it was revealed that management of hospitality and tourism industry needs tight security control for their online activities, fraud prevention with sophisticated anti-fraud tools is necessary in hospitality and tourism industry, improved fraud detection can help to reduce fraud losses in hospitality and tourism industry, the use of anti-fraud tools in hospitality and tourism industry preserves customer loyalty by reassuring members that their data and points are secure, hospitality industry visual analytics is good for identifying suspicious point transfer activity in hospitality and tourism industry, hospitality industry visual analytics is good for identifying suspicious point transfer activity in hospitality and tourism industry and staff of hospitality and tourism industry could make use of vendor tools, including features such as web behavior detection, alert/case management, and link analysis

Hence, there was significant ways of preventing online fraud in the Hospitality and tourism industry. The null hypothesis three which was rejected confirmed that there were significant ways of preventing online fraud in the Hospitality and tourism industry.

Conclusion

Since some business owners in the hotel and tourism industry do not have plans to lessen the impact of identity theft, this study concludes that enterprises in this sector suffer from lower profitability as a result of this crime. Businesses were able to lessen the impact of identity theft because to improved technology, training, and vigilant measures taken by owners, according to the findings. The security agent, directors, businesspeople, hospitality industry and regulatory bodies that make up the core business in the hospitality industry are among the stakeholders who are made aware of the inadequacy and ineffectiveness of security measures in the hospitality and tourism industries.

Recommendations

Based on the results of this study, the following recommendation were made:

1. The hotel and tourism industries must constantly upgrade their security features and designs because if they fall behind, their facilities would be easier targets for criminals.
2. It is the responsibility of the owner of the hotel business to ensure the safety and security of all customers who visit themselves. It is important to inform the owner of a hospitality business that they might be held legally responsible if they fail to address this matter.
3. Every prominent location in the hotel business ought to have a surveillance system installed.
4. Control room: No hospitality business is complete without a specialised control room where a security officer keeps a close eye on all operations. It is imperative that the security guard on patrol promptly notifies the officer watching from the control room of any suspect items, cars, people, or activities so that the latter can conduct an investigation.
5. Customer luggage must be scanned for monitoring.
6. Guests' visitors should be given a 'visitors pass', and their details must be noted on the visitors' register. All the guests should be informed to carry their visitor's pass at all times while in the hospitality industry premises. As this will reduce unnecessary checks by security personnel in the hospitality industry.
7. Frequent security surveys must be carried out by the security section at the hospitality industry. since hospitality and tourism industry environment is very busy. It should also not be prompted by the incidents since this might make the hospitality industry suffer severe financial losses,

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